

Preprint: Explanations of economic inequality as a driver of emotional distress

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Abstract

The way people explain poverty in their society has been studied as a cause and driver of anxiety and discomfort. Negative emotions such as anger and aggression towards people in poverty are dominant when poverty is attributed to factors perceived as being under personal control, which include laziness and lack of willingness. In contrast, positive emotions dominate when poverty is attributed to external factors. Nevertheless, a criticism of these studies is that they have focused almost exclusively on asking respondents why people are poor or the reasons for poverty in their country. We point out that framing economic inequalities mainly as poverty runs the risk of making the system of relationships and social dynamics between economically advantaged and disadvantaged groups invisible, thus leading to a limitation in the study of emotional distress. To address this knowledge gap, we conducted an instrumental phase ($n = 605$) to identify distinct emotional responses to both economically disadvantaged and advantaged groups, as well as to economic inequality itself. Building on these findings, we carried out representative online population surveys in France, Great Britain, and Sweden ($n = 9,000$) to examine in greater detail the emotional responses elicited by different inequality-related stimuli and their relation to causal attributions. Differences in emotional responses to income and wealth inequality were minimal in France and Sweden and almost non-existent in Britain; however, they contrasted markedly with the emotions directed at specific groups such as poor people, rich people, social beneficiaries, and taxpayers. Moreover, we found systematic interrelations between emotions towards income and wealth inequality and the corresponding causal attributions in all three countries. Attributing economic inequality to disadvantaged individuals (relative to blaming the government) was linked to reduced experiences of sadness, moral outrage, anger, and frustration in response to both income and wealth inequality. Our findings suggest that emotional responses to economic inequality are likely multi-targeted and multi-valent, depending on how inequality is framed via different stimuli and on differences in perceived causal attributions.

Keywords: Emotions, inequality attributions, perceptions of inequality, income inequality, wealth inequality

Introduction

Economic inequality is not only about material disparities but also a phenomenon that prompts judgements regarding its causes and evokes emotional responses. Some people attribute economic hardship to individual shortcomings, such as lack of effort, while others emphasise structural factors, such as limited opportunities or unfair institutions. These causal attribution processes, in turn, are closely intertwined with the emotions individuals experience when confronted with inequality. The present study, conducted in three European countries, investigates which emotions are elicited by different inequality-related stimuli and how these emotional responses are systematically linked to distinct causal explanations of income vs. wealth inequality.

Attribution Theory to Economic Outcomes

Attribution theory explores how individuals interpret and explain the causes of events, behaviours, and outcomes in their own lives and the lives of others. Pioneered by Heider (1958), the theory originally distinguishes between internal attributions, which assign causality to personal traits or choices, and external attributions, which attribute outcomes to situational factors, and describes, in turn, how these explanations would shape attitudes and behaviour.

When examining how people explain poverty, extensive research has shown that when hardship is attributed to internal causes, such as laziness, lack of foresight, or personal incompetence, poor individuals are perceived as personally responsible for their condition (Weiner, 2006; Feldman & Crandall, 2007). This leads to lower helping behaviours and less support for policies aimed at reducing economic differences (Osborne & Weiner, 2015; Yúdica et al., 2021).

Conversely, when poverty is explained by external causes beyond personal control—such as limited educational opportunities, scarce job prospects, or physical disability—attributions emphasise structural rather than individual responsibility and promote interventions targeting the system (Cozzarelli et al., 2001; Feldman & Crandall, 2007; Reyna & Reparaz, 2014; Yúdica et al., 2021). Nevertheless, we identify an important gap in the literature regarding *economic*

inequality attributions. A recent review covering fifty years of accumulated evidence on how people explain economic outcomes raises important criticisms (Bastias et al., 2024): studies on attributions focus almost exclusively on poverty rather than economic inequality, a major gap in this field of study. Indeed, compared to the large body of studies on attributions for poverty and poor people, there is a reduced number of studies on economic inequality attributions (for some exceptions, see, Kafetsios & Kateri, 2022; Kluegel & Smith, 1986; Kraus, Piff, & Keltner, 2009).

Drawing a distinction between poverty and economic inequality seems fundamental. Using these terms should not be interchangeable, nor should their meanings be taken as equivalents. Studies of how laypeople understand poverty repeatedly show that poverty is typically used as a descriptive concept highlighting the state of deprivation experienced by an individual or a group of people (Bastias & Barreiro, 2023; Denegri et al., 2010; Reyes & Santiago, 2011). This focus may be problematic, as it frames economic differences as an issue of the disadvantaged group rather than as a structural problem and a matter of justice. Indeed, to explain differences in economic outcomes, the lens through which we view economic inequality may offer a more *relational* and *process-oriented* understanding of individuals' economic struggles than focusing only on separate parts of this relationship, e.g., the poor, the rich or the middle class (Bastias et al., 2024).

In this study, we focus on attributions of economic inequality, taking a novel approach by specifically distinguishing between income and wealth. It is important to note that the distinction between income and wealth inequality is not always apparent to the general public (Mengel and Weidenholzer, 2023). For instance, a recent study based on a representative Dutch population survey shows that people often rely on information about income to calculate wealth distribution and vice versa, revealing confusion between these two types of inequality (Douenne et al., 2024). In light of the scarce research on this matter (Douenne et al., 2024; Mengel and Weidenholzer, 2023), our study provides an opportunity to examine whether framing economic

inequality as income or wealth differences elicits comparable causal attributions and also emotional responses.

Appraisals and Emotional Responses to Inequality

Causal attribution can be considered one component of the *appraisal* process, especially as it relates to the assessment of agency and responsibility (Roseman, 2011). *Appraisal theory* has shown how individuals' interpretation of events and situations shapes their emotional responses more than the event itself and that this appraisal does not need to play out at the level of consciousness or even to be accurate (Redlawsk & Mattes, 2022). According to this theory, emotions arise from unique patterns of appraisal outcomes across different dimensions, including motivational state (appetitive/aversive) and agency (self/others/circumstances), amongst others. For example, according to Roseman (2011), aversive emotions with a feeling of low agency, i.e. control, over the situation are sadness and fear. These emotions typically motivate avoidance or withdrawal behaviours. By contrast, anger, contempt and disgust are emotions holding a high agency potential, i.e., they tend to emerge when the individual feels power over the problem they face (Roseman, 2011). Importantly, though, contempt and disgust are aversive in nature, while anger is appetitive and, therefore, recognised for its mobilising effects (Lee & Lang, 2009). Angry people are motivated to modify the situation, force a change in others' behaviour and even hurt the identified transgressor (Fisher & Roseman, 2007). Another crucial difference between anger and contempt is that the latter is elicited by perceptions that others are inferior — being incompetent, corrupt, foolish, etc. — (Fischer & Roseman, 2007; Hutcherson & Gross, 2011), thus being a trait-focused and person-centred emotion (Roseman, 2018). Finally, and although some authors may not consider indifference as an emotion, others conceptualize it as a state of reduced emotional sensitivity — but an emotion, after all — toward a stimulus that would normally elicit a specific emotional response (Price et al., 2009). Importantly, we highlight that indifference should not be equated with a mere state of stillness in the absence of a stimulus. In indifference, a stimulus is present and a

reaction is expected, yet the anticipated emotion does not emerge, with indifference dampening the anticipated response.

Emotions can also be categorised as a *moral emotion* when they are elicited in response to a perceived moral violation regardless of whether the individual is harmed by the perceived moral transgression (Haidt, 2003). The source of moral motivation should not be to protect one's interests or those of the in-group, but rather to uphold moral principles (Batson et al., 2009; Hechler & Kessler, 2018). Sympathy and compassion, for instance, can be regarded as moral emotions when they arise in response to another's suffering or need caused by an immoral action (Tangney, Stuewig & Mashek, 2007). What is more, shame and guilt can emerge in the individual if they or members of their in-group are understood to be the perpetrators of an immoral act (Lambert, Eadeh & Hanson, 2019). In the case of anger, it can be conceived as a moral emotion when, for instance, it is generated by government decisions regarding certain citizens, as long as the individual experiencing the anger is not personally affected by those decisions (Redlawsk & Mattes, 2022), also termed as empathic anger (Batson et al., 2007)¹. Nevertheless, literature on emotions is increasingly employing the concept of *moral outrage* to describe a feeling provoked by the perception that a moral standard has been violated by the system, the government, authorities and/or any third party (Bastias & Cañadas, 2021; Krauth-Guber & Bonnot, 2020; Thomas et al., 2009). The main trigger here is clearly the violation of a moral standard and not self-interest being harmed. In this vein, we claim that it is relevant to identify to identify the perceived cause of the transgression, and for reason, we believe that attribution processes can shed light on this matter as antecedent appraisals.

In the perceptual process, presenting an economic-related stimulus can trigger explanations about the perceived situation or person, which in turn will shape emotional responses to the former. This has already been well documented by studies in the early 1970s (Feagin, 1972) and further explored by Weiner and colleagues (Weiner, 1980; Zucker & Weiner, 1993), who

¹ The concept of *personal anger* refers to situations when the transgression is perceived to be against oneself and *empathic anger* when someone important to the individual is being affected (Batson et al., 2007).

extended attributional research to economic outcomes. More specifically, if poverty is associated with low personal responsibility of the poor, sympathy and compassion towards poor people are more likely to arise (Cozzarelli et al., 2001; Feldman & Crandall, 2007; Reyna & Reparaz, 2014; Yúdica et al., 2021). This usually sets in when causes of external controllability such as a lack of educational opportunities, work opportunities or physical disability are attributed to explain poverty. Conversely, when poverty is perceived to be subject to personal control, the dominant emotions elicited by these attributions are non-empathic anger-related because of their attributed individual laziness or lack of talent (Feldman & Crandall, 2007; Weiner, 2006). However, interestingly, participants may express anger toward the person — rather than moral outrage toward the situation—, even when prompted by a survey question that frames “poverty” as a situation or circumstance rather than targeting poor individuals directly. This underscores the importance of carefully distinguishing which dimensions or aspects of economic hardship are presented to participants and to keep in mind individuals' limited cognitive capacity to draw clear conceptual lines when answering to survey questions in an expected consistent and coherent manner.

People’s reactions are strongly shaped by how information is presented (Chong & Druckman, 2007; Tversky & Kahneman, 1981). Research on framing indicates that even descriptions of inequality, which typically entail comparisons, tend to focus on the disadvantaged rather than the advantaged group (Lowery et al., 2007). This may be problematic for inequality reduction. For example, in the domain of gender differences, a study reported that participants who read about women’s disadvantage suggested more interventions aimed at helping or changing women (e.g., special training, mentoring and networking programmes, female role models), whereas participants exposed to descriptions focused on men, as the advantaged group, suggested a higher proportion of interventions aimed at systemic changes (Bruckmüller and Braun, 2020). As for economic inequality, Chow and Galak (2012) provide evidence that when income inequality is framed as the poor making less than the rich (as opposed to the rich making more than the poor), US conservatives were less willing to support redistributive tax policies.

Although our interest here does not aim at the consequences of framing for redistributive preferences, but at differing emotional experiences, these results emphasise the importance of framing of inequality cues.

That said, the current study examines, as a secondary objective, whether the manner in which economic inequality is framed — by means of addressing a particular type or representation of economic inequality — affects individuals' emotional responses to it. Especially for public opinion research, where responses are also impacted by the specific formulation of survey questions (Kangas, 1997), it is essential to examine how different types of prompts or stimuli generate distinct emotional responses, which may, in turn, influence individuals' political behaviour. In this study, we decided to explore and compare emotions towards different inequality-related stimuli. Considering that inequality is an inherently relational phenomenon, we measure a broad set of emotions elicited by different types of advantaged (rich people and taxpayers) or disadvantaged (poor people and social beneficiaries) groups or by income and wealth inequality, respectively. For instance, addressing poor and rich people or social beneficiaries and taxpayers may evoke individual-focused emotions like compassion or admiration, while discussing wealth or income inequality may evoke emotional responses that are not necessarily tied to specific groups but may rather be system-oriented, and, therefore, conducive to moral outrage. However, differences between income and wealth are expected, with wealth inequality potentially eliciting admiration for the prosperity and perceived talent of the rich, while simultaneously being associated with a reduced experience of compassion towards the disadvantaged. This may occur even when the stimulus frames inequality in terms of income or wealth, as participants still bear in mind the individuals involved in the unequal relationship.

Hypotheses

From this vantage point, this study investigates the following questions. First, to whom do people in Britain, France and Sweden attribute the causes of income and wealth inequality and

how are these causal attributions associated with the emotions elicited in response to income and wealth inequality? And second, which emotions are elicited in response to different inequality-related stimuli? We then hypothesise:

H1. Causes of both income and wealth inequality will be attributed primarily to external structural factors, rather than to economically disadvantaged groups, with government consistently identified as the principal agent across national settings.

H2. Specific types of attributions will be differentially salient depending on the type of inequality: trade unions will play a more prominent role in attributions for income inequality, whereas rich people will be more frequently held accountable for wealth inequality.

H3. Causal explanations of economic inequality referring to external actors (e.g., the government, rich people, private companies or trade unions) will be more likely associated with emotions like anger, sadness, frustration, and moral outrage towards income or wealth inequality, whereas attributing economic inequality to disadvantaged individuals will more likely be associated with indifference.

H4. When economic inequality is framed in terms of wealth, emotional responses are expected to reflect increased admiration for the advantaged alongside a corresponding decrease in compassion, compared with an income-based framing.

Guided by our hypotheses, we designed our empirical study in two stages. First, we conducted an instrumental study aimed at identifying an appropriately wide range of emotional responses toward both economically advantaged and disadvantaged groups, as well as toward the two dimensions of economic inequality. Second, drawing on these insights, we then selected a set of eight emotions to be examined in our representative online surveys administered in France, Great Britain, and Sweden, with the goal of exploring the associations between emotional responses to and causal attributions of economic inequality.

Nevertheless, while remaining sensitive to information, representations, and cues about inequality, our conceptualisation assumes that both inequality attributions and emotional responses to inequality are embedded in the ‘moral economies’ of welfare regimes (see, for example, Mau, 2003). From a political science perspective, their origins and malleability can thus be understood as products of socialisation and politicisation within a given society. The selection of countries in this study is grounded in this framework: France, Sweden, and Great Britain were chosen as case studies corresponding to Esping-Andersen’s (1990) three types of welfare regimes, i.e., conservative, social-democratic, and liberal. That said, the present study does not aim to provide an in-depth account of the political origins of inequality perceptions, a subject extensively addressed in political science. Instead, our emphasis lies on the psychological dimension, drawing on social psychological literature on emotions and attributions, while complementing the interpretation of our findings with attention to the rationale behind the choice of cases.

Methods

Participants of the instrumental study and the representative online surveys

As a preliminary stage to the main data collection, the instrumental study was conducted with two independent samples: 304 participants in France and 301 participants in Great Britain in May 2024. In the French sample, participants’ ages ranged from 18 to 92 years ($M = 48.5$, $SD = 17.4$), while in the British sample, ages ranged from 18 to 90 years ($M = 48.8$, $SD = 17.3$). With regard to gender, the French sample comprised 147 males (48.4%), 154 females (50.7%), 2 participants identifying as “Other” (0.7%), and 1 participant who selected “Can’t choose” (0.2%). The British sample included 147 males (48.8%) and 154 females (51.2%).

The main empirical study consisted of three representative online surveys administered by a French survey agency, including samples of 3,012 participants in France, 3,008 in Great Britain, and 3,000 in Sweden, all aged 18 or older. In the British sample, participants’ ages ranged from

18 to 94 years ($M = 48.74$, $SD = 17.89$), with 1,556 males (51.8%), 1,438 females (47.9%), and 7 participants selecting “Can't choose” (0.2%). In the French sample, ages ranged from 18 to 93 years ($M = 49.54$, $SD = 17.41$), with 1,434 males (47.6%), 1,574 females (52.3%), and 4 participants selecting “Can't choose” (0.1%). In the Swedish sample, participants' ages ranged from 18 to 92 years ($M = 47.96$, $SD = 17.92$), with 1,518 males (50.6%), 1,476 females (49.2%), and 5 participants selecting “Can't choose” (0.2%)². For additional details on sociodemographic characteristics of the three countries, please refer to Tables S4–S6 in the supplementary materials.

We put into place quality controls in order to prevent duplicates and to identify and eliminate participants who completed the questionnaire in less than 25% of the reported median *length of interview* ($Md = 15:45$ minutes). Additionally, an attention check question was included towards the end of the questionnaire to ensure that respondents continued to be attentive. Before the administration of the main fieldwork, a 'soft launch' was conducted by the survey company, meaning that the survey was initially distributed by the survey agency to a small subset of participants in order to test the functioning of the survey platform (e.g., filter logic and technical features). This preliminary phase allowed us to detect and correct potential issues prior to the start of the full data collection. Data collection was conducted in France and Great Britain between June and July 2024,³ and in Sweden between May and July 2025. This research is part of a larger project with preregistered hypotheses (<https://aspredicted.org/qrw3-v55h.pdf>). The preregistration includes multiple hypotheses related to different facets of the project. The main hypothesis of this paper—proposing that explanations of economic inequality drive emotional responses to inequality—corresponds to H2 in the preregistration, while other hypotheses of this work emerged after pre-registration. This research was carried out in compliance with the ethical standards of the European Research Council. Ethical approval was obtained from the appropriate Institutional Review Board/Ethics Committee, and informed consent was collected

² In the French sample, in addition to age, gender and regions, quotas were also established by socio-professional categories and agglomeration size.

³ In France, the survey ended before the second round of the national election and in Great Britain before the general election.

from all participants prior to their participation in the study. The questionnaire used and the dataset are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17238374>.

Instrumental Study

To decide the set of emotions to be measured in our subsequent representative surveys, we first conducted an *Instrumental Study* (Montero & León, 2007). Instrumental studies are conceived as studies that focus on creating, refining or adapting tests and measurement instruments as well as analysing their psychometric properties. They are commonly developed and implemented in the first research phase. In our case, the need for an instrumental study was due to the scarcity of research that comprehensively explore different emotional responses to different primes of economic inequality.

Prior to our instrumental study, nevertheless, it is important to highlight previous research and its findings, as these constitute the point of departure for the present paper. Specifically, this study is embedded in a five-year framework of a research project funded by the European Research Council, which investigates different facets of the politicization of economic inequality across five methodologically distinct work packages⁴. The first work package consisted of 24 online focus group sessions ($n = 145$; $M_{\text{age}} = 44.2$; $SD = 13.17$), à 90 minutes and conducted with participants from Britain, France, and Sweden (eight focus groups per country with six participants on average per focus group) in 2022. While the primary aim of these sessions was to understand the shortcuts and heuristics individuals employ when forming perceptions of economic inequality, the discussions also revealed emotional responses to inequality. In this regard, the interview guide included, on one hand, a direct question on emotions (*What kind of emotions do you feel when you're confronted with clues of economic inequality, with those signals that we've been talking about?*). On the other hand, at the conclusion of each session, participants completed a short questionnaire measuring, amongst

⁴ To learn more about the project (omitted for double-blind review process), visit: (omitted for double-blind review process).

others, their emotional reactions to three distinct stimuli of inequality: disparities in income and wealth, people living from social benefits, and people earning substantially more than themselves. Here, participants were asked to choose up to three out of the 14 emotions offered in the questionnaire: indifference, jealousy, frustration, powerlessness, anger, hostility, shame, compassion, helplessness, hopelessness, sadness, guilt, anxiety, and hate. Additionally, two response options were included: “can't choose” and “None of the above, other:”, allowing respondents to specify emotions not listed otherwise. As we reported previously (omitted for the double-blind review process), the most prevalent emotional responses to economic inequality were sadness, frustration, compassion, powerlessness, and anger. Interestingly, participants’ emotional responses toward social beneficiaries were, to a considerable extent, feelings of compassion — especially in Britain — while indifference predominated with respect to more affluent individuals, particularly in France (see Table S1 in the supplementary materials).

The subsequently conducted instrumental study included a sample of 605 participants in total. The questionnaire was divided into two modules to select our final set of emotions and to explore different approaches for measuring emotional responses. Module A, comprising 150 participants per country, consisted of a closed-ended question asking about emotions elicited by income inequality and rich people: *“When you think about [income inequality/rich people] in [country], what emotions do you feel? Please choose no more than three of the following options.”* Seventeen emotions⁵ were listed with dichotomous response options (yes/no), followed by the question: *“Among the emotions you selected in the previous question, which one is the strongest? (Choose only one answer).”* In analyzing Module A, the first criterion for selecting emotions was frequency, such that the most frequently endorsed emotions were included in the final survey. Nine emotions emerged consistently across both countries: indifference, moral outrage, powerlessness, admiration, frustration, disgust, anger, sadness, and compassion (See Table S2 and Table S3 in the supplementary materials). The second criterion

⁵ The seventeen different emotions included were: indifference, moral outrage, admiration, powerlessness, frustration, disgust, anger, hostility, jealousy, sadness, shame, helplessness, hopelessness, compassion, anxiety, guilt, and hate. We also added “none of the above, other:” and “can't choose”.

considered the co-occurrences of emotions, assessed using Chi-squared measures, since respondents could initially select up to three emotions. A frequent co-occurrence was observed between disgust, powerlessness, moral outrage, and anger (See Figure S1 in the supplementary materials). Within this constellation, we chose to focus on anger and moral outrage at the system for our final set, given the consistent body of evidence demonstrating their association with perceptions of unfair procedures and distributive outcomes — particularly in the context of economic inequality — (Mikula et al., 1998; Weiss et al., 1999; García-Castro et al., 2020; García-Castro et al., 2022; Vezzoli et al., 2022; Wakslak et al., 2007).

Module B, also with 150 participants per country, included an open-ended question: “*When you think about [income inequality/rich people] in [country], what emotions do you feel?*” This format allowed us to capture emotions that were not anticipated in the closed-ended format but could still be relevant to participants. The results largely aligned with those from Module A in terms of the most frequently elicited emotions. However, they also revealed that some emotional responses were positive (e.g., happy, good, fine), particularly when the stimulus involved rich people. Based on these findings, we incorporated the emotion contentment into the final set. Accordingly, the online questionnaires included the following eight emotions: sadness, frustration, admiration, moral outrage, anger, indifference, compassion, and contentment.

Survey Measures

For the main data collection across the representative national online samples, we used a survey questionnaire divided into two sections: a common core section completed by all respondents, representing 70% of the questionnaire, and a modular section comprising the remaining 30%. In the modular section, participants were randomly assigned to one of four modules: Module A assessed emotions towards income inequality, towards poor and rich individuals, as well as attributions for income inequality; Module B assessed emotions towards income inequality, towards social beneficiaries and taxpayers, and attributions for income inequality; Module C

assessed emotions towards wealth inequality, towards poor and rich individuals, as well as attributions for wealth inequality; and Module D, finally, assessed emotions towards wealth inequality, towards social beneficiaries and taxpayers, as well as attributions for wealth inequality. Each module was completed by at least 750 participants per country.

The rationale for dividing the questionnaire into modules was to prevent potential priming effects from being exposed to multiple types of inequality (income or wealth) or multiple advantaged (rich people or taxpayers) and disadvantaged groups (poor people or social beneficiaries) in sequence. Each participant was therefore presented with only one type of economic inequality and a single pair of target groups (one advantaged, one disadvantaged) capturing participants' responses without interference from prior stimuli.

Demographic variables. Amongst these variables, we included age, gender, household income, subjective social status and level of education.

Emotions. As outlined above, we measured eight emotions (anger, moral outrage, contentment, frustration, indifference, compassion, admiration, and sadness) towards six different inequality stimuli (income inequality, wealth inequality, poor people, rich people, social beneficiaries and taxpayers). The questions were formulated as follows: *When you think about [stimulus] in [country], to what extent do you feel the following emotions? Please place yourself on a score where 1 means "not at all" and 5 means "extremely"*. Participants had to respond to each of the eight presented emotions without the possibility of selecting only a few. Additionally, we included "can't choose" as response option. In our questionnaire, we chose not to include an Information Box with academic definitions of income and wealth inequality. Rather than examining emotional responses triggered by definitions provided by the researchers, our aim was to examine the responses elicited by participants' own notions and everyday understandings of these phenomena, and to assess whether the two constructs generated different emotional reactions.

Causal attributions of economic inequality. In order to measure causal attributions, we drew on the widely tested question wording of the Social Inequality module of the International Social Survey Program (1999, 2009, 2019) but re-formulated it into "*Looking at the list below, who do you think is the main cause of the [income (Module A and B)/wealth (Module C and D)] differences between people with high [income (Module A and B)/wealth (Module C and D)] and people with low [income (Module A and B)/wealth (Module C and D)]?*" The response options were: *Private companies, government, trade unions, high-[income (Module A and B)/wealth (Module C and D)] individuals themselves, low-[income (Module A and B)/wealth (Module C and D)] individuals themselves, other cause: [free text box], and can't choose.*"⁶.

Political Ideology. To account for potential confounding factors aiming to isolate the specific effects of income and wealth inequality attributions on emotional responses, we measure Political Ideology as control variable. We used the following question: "In political matters, people talk of "the left" and "the right." How would you place your views on a scale of 0-10, generally speaking?" The answer was presented as a horizontal scale, running from 0 (left) to 10 (right). We also included "can't choose" as response option.

Results

Causal attributions for income and wealth inequality

We first present an examination of perceived causal attributions for income and wealth inequality in all three countries, followed by a descriptive analysis of emotional responses to income and wealth inequality, to conclude with an inferential exploration of the relationship between causal attributions emotions. With regard to causal attributions for inequality, Figure 1 illustrates public perceptions of the main causes of inequality by income and wealth disparities and by country. Government was identified as the primary cause of both income and wealth

⁶ The response option "Other cause" was excluded from the primary analysis due to its low frequency and the considerable diversity of responses, which prevented the identification of a coherent sixth cause of inequality. Specifically, "Other cause" was selected by 3.2% of participants in Britain, 3.9% in France, and 4.1% in Sweden for causal attributions of income inequality; and by 2.4% in Britain, 4.3% in France, and 2.1% in Sweden for causal attributions of wealth inequality.

inequality by more than 38 per cent of respondents in all three countries. French respondents held their government to a slightly larger percentage share responsible than the British and the Swedish.

Figure 1

Inequality attributions of income and wealth inequality in France, Great Britain and Sweden in %

Note. Percentages displayed in the graphs are rounded. For readability, the label ‘High-wealth individuals’ encompasses both high-wealth and high-income individuals.

Interestingly, the second perceived main cause for inequality in the three countries was private companies, for income inequality, and well-off people, for wealth inequality. Private companies are mentioned by more people in France than in Britain and Sweden to explain income inequality. Finally, in none of the countries studied were trade unions found to be an important cause of economic inequality. Finally, it is worth mentioning that more than 10% of respondents opted for the “can't choose” response category between the listed causal attributions; a reflection on this finding will be taken up in the discussion section.

Table 1: *Within-country differences in causal attributions for income and wealth disparities*

Attribution	Chi2	Fisher's Test	Freq. income	Freq. wealth
Britain				
Private companies	5.17*	0.02	246	202
Government	0.10	0.77	637	635
Trade unions	0.65	0.47	51	44
High-income/wealth individuals	17.58**	0.00	188	273
Low-income/wealth individuals	3.70	0.06	149	120
Can't choose	0.21	0.66	181	192
Other cause	-	-	48	36
<i>N</i>			1,500	1,502
France				
Private companies	46.78**	0.00	339	195
Government	0.05	0.85	583	586
Trade unions	7.34*	0.01	64	37
High-income/wealth individuals	43.42**	0.00	175	307
Low-income/wealth individuals	0.07	0.82	91	94
Can't choose	2.20	0.14	195	222
Other cause	-	-	58	65
<i>N</i>			1,505	1,506
Sweden				
Private companies	8.99**	0.00	221	165
Government	0.20	0.66	640	653
Trade unions	0.31	0.57	44	38
High-income/wealth individuals	4.71*	0.03	198	241
Low-income/wealth individuals	0.10	0.75	143	137
Can't choose	4.60*	0.03	192	234
Other cause	-	-	62	32
<i>N</i>			1,500	1,500

As reported in Table 1, significant differences in attributions were observed between income and wealth inequality in all three countries. High-income/wealth individuals were causally attributed more to wealth inequality than to income inequality (for GB, $\chi^2 = 17.58$, $p < .001$; for FR, $\chi^2 = 43.43$, $p < .001$; for SE, $\chi^2 = 4.71$, $p = 0.03$), while private companies received greater 'blame' for income than for wealth inequality (for GB, $\chi^2 = 5.17$, $p = 0.02$; for FR, $\chi^2 = 46.79$, $p < .001$; for SE, $\chi^2 = 8.99$, $p < .01$). Attributions to the government and low-income/wealth individuals did not show significant differences across income and wealth inequality in either country. Related to H2, trade unions as a cause showed a significant difference only in France ($\chi^2 = 7.34$, $p = 0.01$), with more attributions for income inequality. Finally, in Sweden, a larger share of participants selected "can't choose" when asked about the causes of wealth inequality ($\chi^2 = 4.60$, $p = 0.03$), suggesting greater uncertainty or ambiguity in identifying the sources of this specific type of economic inequality.

Emotional responses to income and wealth inequality

Participants from all three countries exhibit heightened moral outrage, anger, and sadness when thinking about income and wealth inequality. Nevertheless, when comparing the three countries, income and wealth inequality elicit notably higher levels of moral outrage and anger in France with statistically significant differences with Britain and Sweden tested by ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey (see Table S7 and Table S8 in the supplementary materials). By contrast, contentment, admiration, indifference, and frustration are more prevalent in Britain than in France and Sweden with statistically significant differences with the exception of admiration towards wealth inequality for the pair Britain-Sweden.

Elicited emotions when thinking of income compared to wealth inequality differ significantly in some cases (see Table 2). In both, France and Sweden, wealth inequality was more strongly linked to admiration, while income inequality elicited stronger responses of anger, frustration, and compassion. France additionally showed higher indifference and contentment in terms of wealth inequality, a pattern not present in Sweden. In contrast, British participants exhibited more balanced emotional responses across the two primes, with only compassion differentiating income from wealth inequality.

Table 2: Comparing and statistically testing emotions between income and wealth inequality as stimulus

	Emotion	Stimulus	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i> (1-5)	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Britain	Sadness	Income	1,422	3.3	1.1	1.35	0.18
		Wealth	1,436	3.3	1.2		
	Moral Outrage	Income	1,418	3.3	1.2	-0.11	0.91
		Wealth	1,427	3.3	1.3		
	Indifference	Income	1,399	2.5	1.2	-1.08	0.28
		Wealth	1,426	2.5	1.3		
	Contentment	Income	1,386	2.1	1.1	-0.90	0.37
		Wealth	1,397	2.1	1.1		
	Anger	Income	1,427	3.3	1.3	1.28	0.20
		Wealth	1,450	3.2	1.3		
	Frustration	Income	1,429	3.5	1.2	0.79	0.43
		Wealth	1,448	3.5	1.2		
	Compassion	Income	1,415	3.3	1.2	3.40	0.00
		Wealth	1,433	3.1	1.2		
Admiration	Income	1,378	2.0	1.1	0.78	0.43	
	Wealth	1,395	2.0	1.1			
France	Sadness	Income	1,465	3.3	1.2	1.52	0.13
		Wealth	1,452	3.2	1.2		
	Moral Outrage	Income	1,453	3.5	1.2	1.65	0.10

		Wealth	1,448	3.5	1.2		
	Indifference	Income	1,467	2.0	1.1	-3.29	0.00
		Wealth	1,450	2.1	1.2		
	Contentment	Income	1,431	1.8	1.0	-2.08	0.04
		Wealth	1,413	1.9	1.0		
	Anger	Income	1,465	3.5	1.3	3.35	0.00
		Wealth	1,461	3.3	1.3		
	Frustration	Income	1,466	3.2	1.3	3.74	0.00
		Wealth	1,454	3.1	1.3		
	Compassion	Income	1,446	3.0	1.3	3.48	0.00
		Wealth	1,433	2.8	1.3		
	Admiration	Income	1,424	1.7	1.0	-2.62	0.01
		Wealth	1,408	1.8	1.1		
<hr/>							
Sweden	Sadness	Income	1,430	3.1	1.2	2.45	0.01
		Wealth	1,420	3.0	1.2		
	Moral Outrage	Income	1,417	3.2	1.2	3.77	0.00
		Wealth	1,416	3.0	1.3		
	Indifference	Income	1,400	2.3	1.2	-1.78	0.08
		Wealth	1,388	2.4	1.1		
	Contentment	Income	1,391	1.8	1.0	-0.87	0.30
		Wealth	1,392	1.9	1.0		
	Anger	Income	1,435	3.0	1.3	3.17	0.00
		Wealth	1,435	2.8	1.3		
	Frustration	Income	1,441	3.3	1.3	3.71	0.00
		Wealth	1,447	3.1	1.3		
	Compassion	Income	1,423	3.3	1.2	3.98	0.00
		Wealth	1,412	3.1	1.2		
	Admiration	Income	1,385	1.8	1.0	-4.73	0.00
		Wealth	1,389	2.0	1.1		

In relation to the other inequality-related stimuli presented, reactions to poor people largely resemble those to income and wealth inequality (see Table S7). However, the emotions elicited by the two disadvantaged groups (social beneficiaries and poor people) differ significantly from each other in terms of sadness and compassion — with social beneficiaries inducing considerably less of these feelings, especially in France. Rich people elicit lower levels of these emotions, with indifference being relatively more pronounced. In general, emotional responses to social beneficiaries and taxpayers are more moderate, showing less intense emotional engagement compared to the other primes.

Inferential exploration of the relationship between attributions and emotions

Building on these descriptive findings, we now turn to inferential analyses to examine the relationships between causal attributions for inequality and emotional responses to different inequality stimuli. As mentioned above (see Methods section), we investigated emotional

responses and causal attributions towards income inequality as well as towards wealth

inequality.

Figure 2: Emotions towards income and wealth inequality experienced by people who explain inequality by different causes.

Note. The five concentric octagons in each radial graph represent the five points of the Likert scale (1–5, from center to edge). ANOVA showed that all mean differences in emotions across causal attributions were significant in the three countries, except for compassion toward income and wealth inequality in France. Trade Unions and Other were excluded as they accounted for less than 5% of responses, and 'Can't choose' was omitted due to lack of specificity.

Table 3: Multiple linear regression analyses of emotional responses to income and wealth inequality stimuli regressed on different causal inequality attributions

		Sadness	Moral Outrage	Anger	Frustration	Compassion	Contentment	Indifference	Admiration	
Income Inequality	Britain	Private companies	-0.18*	-0.18*	-0.26***	-0.23***	-0.12	-0.10	0.03	0.01
		High-income individuals	-0.12	-0.11	-0.07	-0.08	0.01	0.12	0.21*	0.11
		Low-income individuals	-0.90***	-0.97***	-0.86***	-0.90***	-0.61***	0.23*	0.34***	0.08
		(Intercept)	0.15***	0.17***	0.16***	0.20***	0.1	0.08	-0.06	0.03
		Adj. R ²	0.14	0.17	0.18	0.17	0.06	0.18	0.14	0.16
		N	1,220	1,219	1,223	1,227	1,213	1,190	1,204	1,204
	France	Private companies	-0.15	-0.11	-0.30***	-0.22***	0.03	0.05	0.13	0.09
		High-income individuals	-0.02	-0.16	-0.27*	-0.16	-0.06	0.18	0.19	0.17
		Low-income individuals	-0.55***	-0.91***	-0.97***	-0.81***	-0.05	0.45***	0.73***	0.33*
		(Intercept)	0.01	0.09	0.15*	0.1	-0.08	0.08	-0.03	0.02
		Adj. R ²	0.08	0.12	0.14	0.12	0.06	0.1	0.12	0.09
		N	1,224	1,221	1,227	1,226	1,214	1,209	1,228	1,199
	Sweden	Private companies	-0.17*	-0.20*	-0.04	-0.18*	-0.07	0.10	0.04	0.10
		High-income individuals	-0.04	-0.11	-0.15	-0.12	0.02	0.07	0.10	0.10
		Low-income individuals	-0.75***	-0.94***	-0.80***	-0.87***	-0.58***	0.11	0.20*	0.06
(Intercept)		-0.03	0.08	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.09	0.07	0.12*	
Adj. R ²		0.19	0.24	0.19	0.22	0.11	0.11	0.09	0.11	
N		1,224	1,218	1,229	1,236	1,217	1,193	1,200	1,197	
Wealth Inequality	Britain	Private companies	-0.30***	-0.31***	-0.38***	-0.20*	-0.17	0.13	0.02	0.20*
		High-income individuals	-0.09	-0.13	-0.13	-0.12	-0.01	-0.02	0.01	0.00
		Low-income individuals	-0.65***	-0.94***	-0.77***	-0.77***	-0.58***	0.44***	0.37***	0.35***
		(Intercept)	0.13*	0.14*	0.14*	0.07	0.09	0.05	0.02	0.00
		Adj. R ²	0.09	0.15	0.17	0.17	0.04	0.20	0.14	0.17
		N	1,228	1,226	1,242	1,240	1,229	1,203	1,219	1,204
	France	Private companies	-0.06	-0.10	-0.19*	-0.29***	0.14	0.14	0.08	0.12
		High-income individuals	-0.02	-0.07	-0.10	-0.18*	0.11	-0.01	0.10	0.06
		Low-income individuals	-0.53***	-0.72***	-0.68***	-0.68***	0.04	0.32*	0.62***	0.40***
		(Intercept)	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.14*	-0.14*	0.13*	0.05	0.01
		Adj. R ²	0.08	0.16	0.14	0.12	0.06	0.12	0.13	0.09
		N	1,220	1,218	1,227	1,221	1,206	1,191	1,216	1,185
	Sweden	Private companies	-0.14	-0.14	-0.21*	-0.27***	-0.09	0.07	-0.04	0.05
		High-income individuals	-0.14	-0.20*	-0.22***	-0.24***	-0.11	0.09	0.09	0.17*
		Low-income individuals	-0.57***	-0.63***	-0.59***	-0.55***	-0.36***	0.40***	0.32***	0.37***
(Intercept)		0.01	0.14***	0.08	0.11*	-0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	
Adj. R ²		0.21	0.20	0.18	0.22	0.09	0.11	0.10	0.12	
N		1,184	1,180	1,194	1,205	1,170	1,165	1,161	1,156	

Note. Control variables included are: Age, Gender, Income, Education, Social subjective status, and political orientation Left–Right. $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***). The reference category for causal attributions is Government. Regression coefficients (b) are reported.

Figure 2 presents the mean levels of emotional responses to income and wealth inequality according to the perceived causal agent: government, private companies, high-income individuals, trade unions, and low-income individuals. When inequality is attributed to the government, respondents tend to report the highest levels of negative emotions, including sadness, moral outrage, anger, and frustration, for both income and wealth inequality. Among these, frustration is the most intense emotion, with mean scores across countries ranging from 3.53 to 3.85 (SDs \approx 0.42–0.47), while positive emotions such as contentment and admiration remain comparatively low (contentment ranges from 1.69 to 2.01; admiration ranges from 1.59 to 1.96). Participants who perceive private companies and high-income individuals as the main cause of income and wealth inequality report moderately high negative emotions, slightly lower than those directed toward the government. Anger and frustration typically fall in the 3.01–3.46 range (SDs \approx 0.52–0.61). By contrast, participants who view low-income individuals as the primary cause of income and wealth inequality report the lowest levels of negative emotions, while indifference tends to be higher. For example, mean sadness scores range from 2.14 to 2.62 (SDs \approx 0.52–0.58), and frustration averages 2.15–2.59.

Emotional responses to income inequality largely resemble those reported for wealth inequality, with several trends remaining consistent across Britain, France, and Sweden. However, in France, mean levels of moral outrage and anger in response to both income and wealth inequality are slightly higher than those observed in Britain and Sweden.

The regressions reported in Table 3 reveal systematic patterns in how causal attributions may be associated with emotional responses to economic inequality. When income inequality is attributed to low-income individuals respondents across Britain, France, and Sweden report markedly lower levels of anger, sadness, frustration, and moral outrage towards income inequality compared to when government is named as the cause. This attenuated emotional response extends to wealth inequality as well, underscoring a tendency to downplay negative affect when disadvantaged groups are held responsible. At the same time, such attributions are positively associated with indifference and, in several cases, with contentment or even admiration,

suggesting a shift away from moralized emotions toward more neutral or even legitimizing orientations. Compassion was also consistently lower when inequality was attributed to economically disadvantaged groups rather than to government in Britain and Sweden, but not in France.

For parsimony and to ensure clarity of interpretation, the categories Trade Unions and Other cause were excluded from the models, as they each accounted for fewer than 5% of responses, and Can't choose was omitted due to its lack of specificity. Importantly, robustness checks (reported in the supplementary materials, Tables S11 and S12) demonstrate that the inclusion or exclusion of these categories does not alter the substantive findings.

Figure 3: Change in adjusted R^2 after the inclusion of (income and wealth) inequality attributions in multiple regression analyses

Our results show that causal attributions of income and wealth inequality are, indeed, meaningfully associated with emotional responses to inequality-related stimuli. This effect occurs independently of the participants' age, gender, household income, subjective social status, years of education, and political ideology (for the

effects of control variables, see Table S9 and S10 in the supplementary materials). As shown in Figure 3, across countries and emotions, model fit improved consistently, with the largest gains for anger, sadness, and moral outrage, while emotions such as admiration and contentment exhibited minimal changes in adjusted R^2 (see also Table S13). These results highlight that including causal attributions adds explanatory value beyond baseline demographic controls.

Discussion

Consistent with our first hypothesis (H1), respondents predominantly attributed both income and wealth inequality to external structural factors rather than to economically disadvantaged groups. Notably, the government emerged as the principal cause of economic inequality across Britain, France, and Sweden. In each country, over 38% of respondents identified the government as responsible, a proportion likely to have significant implications for political trust, voting behaviour, and broader political participation. Identifying the government as a distinct factor among different external factors represents a relatively novel approach within research on causal attributions, which has traditionally categorised explanations as individualistic, fatalistic, or structural (Bullock et al., 2003; Cozzarelli et al., 2001; Feagin, 1972; Furnham, 1982). While structural attributions conventionally encompass government influence, they are typically not disaggregated but rather grouped alongside broader systemic factors, such as labour market dynamics, societal structures, discrimination, or the capitalist system writ large. Based on the evidence presented here, we emphasise the importance of explicitly incorporating the government as a distinct causal factor in future studies, particularly given the current context of political distrust and democratic backsliding in European societies.

Our study also shows relevant within-country differences in the way that people explain income vs. wealth inequality. Concerning causal attributions, high-income and high-wealth individuals were more often held responsible for wealth inequality than for income inequality, whereas private companies received greater attribution of responsibility for income than for wealth inequality, in all three countries. These results confirm our hypothesis (H2), suggesting that specific types of attributions are differentially salient depending on the

type of economic inequality, highlighting the importance of explicitly distinguishing between income and wealth inequality in future research.

Regarding our third hypothesis (H3), we anticipated that causal explanations of economic inequality—both income and wealth—that attribute responsibility for economic outcomes to disadvantaged individuals would be associated with lower levels of anger and moral outrage towards different inequality-related stimuli. The palliative effects of legitimising existing economic structures have been widely documented in previous research (Harding & Sibley, 2013; Jost et al., 2008; Vargas-Salfate et al., 2018; Wakslak et al., 2007).

However, the role of causal attributions of inequality has not yet been explicitly examined as a psychological mechanism contributing to the preservation of society's emotional well-being. In this study, we extend the literature by presenting evidence that feelings of sadness, anger, moral outrage, and frustration are less frequently experienced by participants who attribute inequality to the personal responsibility of economically disadvantaged individuals compared to external factors, in all three countries and irrespective of the welfare regime type. By contrast, participants who absolve poor people of personal responsibility are more likely to experience higher levels of negative emotions. Accordingly, we argue that individuals may be motivated to justify social inequalities by attributing economic outcomes rather to personal responsibility as a means to mitigate uncomfortable emotions elicited by thinking about economic inequality. In other words, the avoidance of such discomfort could be a key factor driving the rationalisation of economic inequalities. We confirm that different explanations of income and wealth inequality have significant emotional implications and extend prior research on the palliative effects of rationalising existing economic arrangements by highlighting causal attributions as a protective mechanism for emotional well-being.

We then examined whether the different inequality-related stimuli elicited distinct emotional experiences. Building on qualitative work (omitted for the double-blind review process) and an instrumental study, we identified eight central emotions for our main survey: sadness, frustration, admiration, moral outrage, anger, indifference, compassion, and contentment. Based on our expectations (H4), we anticipated that wealth-based framings of inequality would elicit more admiration for the advantaged and, in turn, lower levels of

compassion compared with income-based framings. Consistent with the aforementioned, we identified a novel pattern of differences in emotional responses to income versus wealth inequality. In both France and Sweden, admiration was primarily associated with wealth inequality, whereas frustration, anger, and compassion were more strongly tied to income inequality. In France alone, however, wealth inequality—relative to income inequality—also elicited higher levels of indifference and contentment, suggesting that in this national context wealth inequality may be more readily overlooked and/or socially tolerated. By contrast, in Britain, income and wealth inequality elicited largely similar emotional reactions, with compassion being the only exception, as it was expressed more strongly in response to income inequality. Accordingly, in the British case, at least with respect to emotional resonance, a clear distinction between income and wealth inequality does not appear to emerge.

Regarding cross-country differences, both income and wealth inequality elicited notably higher levels of moral outrage and anger in France, whereas contentment, admiration, indifference, and frustration were more prevalent in Britain. These emotions experienced in Britain in relation to economic inequality typically motivate avoidance or withdrawal behaviours; for instance, frustration generally arises when an obstacle prevents an individual from achieving a desired goal, in this case, equality (Roseman, 2011). These results align with the logic of the liberal welfare regime, where inequality is more readily accepted as a consequence of merit or market mechanisms (Esping-Andersen, 1990). Within this framework, frustration may reflect private discomfort in the face of individual obstacles rather than collective indignation against an unjust system. By contrast, anger and moral outrage in France are highly politically mobilising emotions, suggesting that individuals feel empowered and motivated to effect change (Lee & Lang, 2009; Roseman, 2011). This pattern corresponds with the strong tradition of collective mobilisation against inequality in French political culture, where indignation serves as a driver of collective action.

An important nuance must be considered regarding anger-related emotions. Previous studies indicate that the dominant emotion elicited by individual attributions of poverty is anger directed at poor people (Feldman & Crandall, 2007; Osborne & Weiner, 2015; Weiner, 2006; Yúdica et al., 2021). However, our findings show

that this very same type of attribution is associated with notably lower levels of anger (and also moral outrage) towards income and wealth inequality. The distinction is relevant since anger toward poor people and anger toward the system of inequality have very different social and political consequences. It is therefore possible that two distinct variants of anger are involved here, arising from different antecedent appraisals. On the one hand, anger may be directed towards individuals in poverty due to perceived laziness or lack of skills; on the other hand, anger may target the system or government, thereby exonerating the poor. The first variant reflects an individual-focused emotion potentially associated with disgust or contempt, whereas the second corresponds to a system-focused emotion aligned with moral outrage.

Overall, this underscores the importance of clearly delineating the object that triggers emotional responses, as well as the differences that arise when economic suffering is framed in terms of individual hardship versus broader structural inequality. Furthermore, we observed important variations in the emotions elicited by different inequality-related stimuli. Compassion was expressed more strongly toward disadvantaged groups, such as the poor and social beneficiaries, whereas indifference predominated in reactions to advantaged groups, particularly rich people and taxpayers. Moreover, when presented with “poor people” as a stimulus, participants from all three countries reported higher levels of individual-oriented emotions—such as sadness, compassion, and admiration—than when responding to income or wealth inequality. Interestingly, however, poor people also elicited levels of moral outrage comparable to those triggered by income and wealth inequality, suggesting that a disadvantage-focused frame centered on the poor can likewise generate system-oriented emotional responses. Unlike those elicited by rich people, social beneficiaries, or taxpayers, prompts concerning poor people appear to be understood in a broader social context, linking them to systems of inequality while simultaneously also eliciting individual-focused emotions.

Although overall levels of indifference were relatively low across the three countries, this response was particularly pronounced when directed towards wealth inequality and also towards rich people. The salience of this pattern in the instrumental study — echoing results from the prior focus group research (omitted for the double-blind review process) — prompted our decision to retain indifference within the emotion

framework. We argue that, unlike a neutral or non-emotional state, indifference carries additional significance because the situation ought to elicit an emotional response, and the absence of such a response motivates interpretation (Cohen-Chen et al., 2022). Future research could explore whether indifference towards the rich functions as a mechanism to avoid self-positioning as poor, particularly when this group is perceived as stigmatised (Condon & Wichowsky, 2020), and how this influences redistributive preferences.

We acknowledge limitations of our study that could be addressed in future research. For instance, in the question regarding the causes of inequality, more than 12% of respondents across the three countries selected the “Can’t choose” response option. This may reflect either a mismatch between the response options and the respondents’ perceptions, or the presence of multiple factors that respondents wished to indicate but the single-response format did not allow for.

To date, research on inequality has often relied on framings that isolate either the disadvantaged or the advantaged, rather than considering the relational nature of inequality itself (for a recent review, see Malapally et al., 2025). In the present study, we emphasize that the concept of *inequality* implies a comparison between at least two parties and is defined by the relationship between them. As an inherently comparative phenomenon, inequality is best understood as a relational concept. Consequently, asking respondents to explain economic differences allows researchers to explore hardship within its broader social context, rather than viewing the poor or the rich in isolation, thereby making the systems and relationships that produce economic disparities (more) salient. It is worth noting that this study is one of the few to examine explanations for economic inequality, both in terms of income and wealth, while also analysing the emotional correlates of these attributions.

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Supplementary Materials for

Explanations of economic inequality as a driver of emotional distress

This file includes:

Tables S1 to S13
Figures S1 and S2

Table S1

Frequencies and means of respondents across countries reporting on a selection of the three most important emotions elicited by three stimuli and conducted in the survey after the focus group sessions, January to February 2022

Emotion	Income and wealth inequality				People living from social benefits				People who have much more money than oneself			
	FR	SE	GB	<i>M</i>	FR	SE	GB	<i>M</i>	FR	SE	GB	<i>M</i>
Indifference	1	0	0	0.33	4	2	4	3.33	25	12	11	16.00
Jealousy	0	0	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00	1	8	9	6.00
Frustration	5	12	9	8.67	3	10	5	6.00	4	8	4	5.33
Powerlessness	16	4	8	9.33	10	3	4	5.67	3	2	5	3.33
Anger	3	5	8	5.33	4	1	1	2.00	4	1	2	2.33
Hostility	1	1	0	0.67	4	0	0	1.33	1	0	4	1.67
Shame	1	0	1	0.67	2	1	0	1.00	1	0	4	1.67
Compassion	2	12	5	6.33	9	14	14	12.33	2	0	2	1.33
Helplessness	2	3	10	5.00	5	5	6	5.33	1	1	1	1.00
Hopelessness	2	4	3	3.00	0	1	1	0.67	1	0	1	0.67
Sadness	14	3	3	6.67	6	3	4	4.33	0	0	1	0.33
Guilt	0	0	1	0.33	0	1	4	1.67	0	1	0	0.33
Anxiety	1	1	0	0.67	1	1	2	1.33	1	0	0	0.33
Hate	1	3	0	1.33	0	1	0	0.33	0	0	0	0.00
<i>N</i>	51	46	48		51	46	48		51	46	48	

Table S2

Emotions reported (up to three per respondent) when thinking about income inequality and rich people in Britain and France: Findings from the Instrumental Study conducted in May 2024

Emotion	Income inequality				Rich people			
	Britain		France		Britain		France	
	<i>freq.</i>	%	<i>freq.</i>	%	<i>freq.</i>	%	<i>freq.</i>	%
Frustration	46	31	26	17	29	19	16	11
Powerlessness	39	26	48	31	13	9	33	22
Moral Outrage	30	20	44	29	25	17	34	22
Sadness	29	20	26	17	12	8	7	5
Disgust	29	19	35	23	16	11	28	18
Anger	27	18	52	34	11	7	19	12
Helplessness	22	15	12	8	11	7	5	3
Hopelessness	16	11	8	5	5	3	7	5
Can't choose	14	9	5	3	20	13	9	6
Indifference	13	9	15	10	43	29	40	26
Compassion	12	8	14	9	4	3	4	3
Anxiety	8	5	11	7	4	3	3	2
Hostility	7	5	4	3	11	7	11	7
Shame	6	4	17	11	2	1	16	11
Jealousy	6	4	4	3	0	0	0	0
None of the above, other	4	3	1	1	5	3	3	2
Guilt	3	2	2	1	3	2	3	2
Hate	3	2	5	3	3	2	2	1
Admiration	3	2	5	3	22	15	25	16

Note. Participants were invited to select up to three emotions from a list of 17 options.
N (Britain) = 150; *N* (France) = 153.

Table S3

Strongest Emotion Selected in Response to Income Inequality and Rich People in Britain and France: Findings from the Instrumental Study conducted in May 2024

Emotion	Income inequality				Rich people			
	Britain		France		Britain		France	
Can't choose	23	15	7	5	30	20	15	10
Frustration	21	14	12	8	11	7	6	4
Powerlessness	18	12	25	16	6	4	19	12
Disgust	18	12	13	9	6	4	17	11
Moral Outrage	15	10	16	11	15	10	18	12
Anger	10	7	30	20	7	5	6	4
Sadness	10	7	9	6	4	3	1	1
Indifference	8	5	12	8	30	20	33	22
Helplessness	7	5	2	1	6	4	2	1
Hopelessness	6	4	5	3	2	1	2	1
Compassion	5	3	5	3	3	2	0	0
Jealousy	3	2	0	0	4	3	2	1
Admiration	3	2	4	3	16	11	16	11
Shame	2	1	9	6	1	1	9	6
Hate	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Anxiety	0	0	4	3	1	1	2	1
Hostility	0	0	0	0	6	4	3	2
None of the above, other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Guilt	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1

Note. Participants indicated which emotion was the strongest among those three they selected in the previous question. N (Britain) = 150; N (France) = 153.

Figure S1

Co-occurrence of emotions reported (up to three per respondent) towards income inequality and rich people in Britain (above the diagonal) and France (below the diagonal)

Note. To quantify the tendency of two emotions to co-occur, correlations were calculated using Pearson's r , which is equivalent to the Phi coefficient for binary (dummy) variables.

Table S4

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the British Sample by Region, Household Income, Subjective Social Status, and Education: Results from the Survey Study conducted in June and July 2024

Region		Household income		Subjective Social Status		Education in Years <i>M (SD)</i>
East Midlands	7.30%	Decile 1	7.20%	1	2.00%	14.71 (4.44)
East of England	8.80%	Decile 2	8.80%	2	2.80%	
London	13.80%	Decile 3	8.60%	3	7.90%	
East	4.00%	Decile 4	9.90%	4	13.00%	
West	11.70%	Decile 5	11.90%	5	23.70%	
Scotland	8.60%	Decile 6	10.10%	6	20.00%	
East	14.40%	Decile 7	10.80%	7	15.00%	
West	9.20%	Decile 8	10.70%	8	6.90%	
Wales	4.90%	Decile 9	7.90%	9	1.60%	
Midlands	8.90%	Decile 10	8.20%	10	1.70%	
Yorkshire and The Humber	8.40%	Can't choose	6.10%	Can't choose	5.40%	
Can't choose	0,0%					

Note. Decile 1 = Less than £1,014; Decile 2 = £1,014 to under £1,409; Decile 3 = £1,409 to under £1,790; Decile 4 = £1,790 to under £2,190; Decile 5 = £2,190 to under £2,659; Decile 6 = £2,659 to under £3,162; Decile 7 = £3,162 to under £3,799; Decile 8 = £3,799 to under £4,617; Decile 9 = £4,617 to under £6,063; Decile 10 = £6,063 or more.

Table S5

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the French Sample by Region, Household Income, Subjective Social Status, and Education: Results from the Survey Study conducted in June and July 2024

Region		Household income		Subjective Social Status		Education in Years <i>M (SD)</i>
Auvergne - Alpes	12.30%	Decile 1	5%	1	3.7%	14.53 (4.31)
Bourgogne - Franche Comté	4.20%	Decile 2	8.7%	2	4.1%	
Bretagne	5.20%	Decile 3	5.5%	3	10.9%	
Centre - Val de Loire	4.00%	Decile 4	8%	4	13.9%	
Grand Est	8.60%	Decile 5	8.3%	5	27.5%	
Hauts-de-France	9.10%	Decile 6	6.9%	6	19.8%	
Ile de France	18.50%	Decile 7	8.6%	7	11.2%	
Normandie	5.00%	Decile 8	8.5%	8	3.9%	
Nouvelle Aquitaine	9.70%	Decile 9	13.8%	9	0.8%	
Occitanie	9.50%	Decile 10	19.7%	10	0.7%	
Pays-de-la-Loire	5.90%	Ne peut choisir	7%	Ne peut choisir	3.5%	
Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur	7.70%					
Ne peut choisir	0.30%					

Note. Decile 1 = Moins de 1,000 euros; Decile 2 = De 1,000 à 1,500 euros; Decile 3 = De 1,501 à 1,700 euros; Decile 4 = De 1,701 à 2,000 euros; Decile 5 = De 2,001 à 2,300 euros; Decile 6 = De 2,301 à 2,600 euros; Decile 7 = De 2,601 à 3,000 euros; Decile 8 = De 3,001 à 3,300 euros; Decile 9 = De 3,301 à 4,000 euros; Decile 10 = Plus de 4,000 euros.

Table S6

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Swedish Sample by Region, Household Income, Subjective Social Status, and Education: Results from the Survey Study conducted between May and July 2025

Region				Household income		Subjective Social Status		Edu. in Years <i>M (SD)</i>
Stockholm	23.60%	Västra Götaland	16.20%	Decile 1	2.10%	1	1.70%	12.86 (4.59)
Uppsala	3.90%	Värmland	2.50%	Decile 2	2.30%	2	2.90%	
Södermanland	3.40%	Örebro	2.60%	Decile 3	11.20%	3	7.10%	
Östergötland	4.80%	Västmanland	2.80%	Decile 4	8.00%	4	9.90%	
Jönköping	3.30%	Dalarna	2.50%	Decile 5	10.10%	5	23.40%	
Kronoberg	1.70%	Gävleborg	2.10%	Decile 6	17.90%	6	20.00%	
Kalmar	2.90%	Västernorrland	2.60%	Decile 7	14.40%	7	19.40%	
Gotland	0.70%	Jämtland	1.00%	Decile 8	8.60%	8	9.40%	
Blekinge	2.10%	Västerbotten	2.20%	Decile 9	8.70%	9	1.60%	
Skåne	13.50%	Norrbottn	2.10%	Decile 10	10.80%	10	1.20%	
Halland	3.40%	Can't choose	0.10%	Can't choose	5.80%	Can't choose	3.40%	

Note. Decile 1 = Upp till 11,999 kr; Decile 2 = 12,000–14,999 kr; Decile 3 = 15,000–20,999 kr; Decile 4 = 21,000–24,999 kr; Decile 5 = 25,000–29,999 kr; Decile 6 = 30,000–37,999 kr; Decile 7 = 38,000–45,999 kr; Decile 8 = 46,000–54,999 kr; Decile 9 = 55,000–69,999 kr; Decile 10 = 70,000 kr eller mer.

Table S7

Means of the emotional responses towards economic inequality-related stimuli (1-5): Results from the Survey Study

	Stimulus	Moral Outrage	Anger	Sadness	Compassion	Frustration	Admiration	Indifference	Contentment
Britain	Income Inequality	3.3 (1.2)	3.3 (1.3)	3.3 (1.1)	3.3 (1.2)	3.5 (1.2)	2.0 (1.1)	2.5 (1.2)	2.1 (1.1)
	Wealth Inequality	3.3 (1.3)	3.2 (1.3)	3.3 (1.2)	3.1 (1.2)	3.5 (1.2)	2.0 (1.1)	2.5 (1.3)	2.1 (1.1)
	Poor People	3.2 (1.3)	3.1 (1.3)	3.6 (1.2)	3.6 (1.1)	3.4 (1.2)	2.3 (1.2)	2.3 (1.2)	1.9 (1.1)
	Social Benef.	2.9 (1.2)	2.9 (1.2)	3.0 (1.2)	3.1 (1.2)	3.1 (1.2)	2.0 (1.2)	2.4 (1.1)	2.1 (1.1)
	Rich People	2.9 (1.4)	2.8 (1.4)	1.9 (1.2)	1.8 (1.1)	2.9 (1.4)	2.3 (1.2)	2.6 (1.3)	2.1 (1.2)
	Taxpayers	2.7 (1.3)	2.8 (1.3)	2.7 (1.2)	2.6 (1.2)	3.0 (1.3)	2.5 (1.2)	2.5 (1.2)	2.3 (1.1)
	France	Income Inequality	3.5 (1.2)	3.5 (1.3)	3.3 (1.2)	3.0 (1.3)	3.2 (1.3)	1.7 (1.0)	2.0 (1.1)
Wealth Inequality		3.5 (1.2)	3.3 (1.3)	3.2 (1.2)	2.8 (1.3)	3.1 (1.3)	1.8 (1.1)	2.1 (1.2)	1.9 (1.0)
Poor People		3.5 (1.2)	3.3 (1.3)	3.7 (1.2)	3.6 (1.1)	3.0 (1.3)	1.8 (1.1)	1.8 (1.1)	1.6 (1.0)
Social Benef.		3.0 (1.3)	3.1 (1.4)	2.7 (1.3)	2.5 (1.3)	2.6 (1.4)	1.6 (1.0)	2.2 (1.2)	1.8 (1.0)
Rich People		2.8 (1.5)	2.7 (1.5)	1.7 (1.1)	1.5 (0.9)	2.5 (1.4)	2.2 (1.3)	2.7 (1.4)	1.9 (1.1)
Taxpayers		2.7 (1.3)	2.8 (1.4)	2.6 (1.3)	2.5 (1.2)	2.8 (1.3)	2.1 (1.2)	2.3 (1.2)	2.1 (1.1)
Sweden		Income Inequality	3.2 (1.2)	3.0 (1.3)	3.1 (1.2)	3.3 (1.2)	3.3 (1.3)	1.8 (1.0)	2.3 (1.2)
	Wealth Inequality	3.0 (1.3)	2.8 (1.3)	3.0 (1.2)	3.1 (1.2)	3.1 (1.3)	2.0 (1.1)	2.4 (1.1)	1.9 (1.0)
	Poor People	3.3 (1.2)	3.0 (1.3)	3.6 (1.2)	3.7 (1.1)	3.3 (1.3)	1.8 (1.1)	2.1 (1.1)	1.6 (1.0)
	Social Benef.	2.7 (1.2)	2.5 (1.3)	3.1 (1.2)	3.2 (1.2)	2.9 (1.2)	1.7 (1.0)	2.2 (1.1)	1.6 (1.0)
	Rich People	2.7 (1.3)	2.6 (1.4)	2.0 (1.2)	1.8 (1.1)	2.7 (1.4)	2.2 (1.2)	2.4 (1.2)	1.9 (1.1)
	Taxpayers	2.5 (1.3)	2.4 (1.3)	2.4 (1.3)	2.6 (1.2)	2.6 (1.3)	2.3 (1.2)	2.2 (1.1)	2.3 (1.2)

Note. Values represent means, with standard deviations in parentheses. ANOVA results comparing the three countries revealed statistically significant differences across all emotions. For pairwise comparisons between countries, see Tukey's post-hoc tests in Table S8. $N = 3,012$ in France, $N = 3,008$ in Great Britain, and $N = 3,000$ in Sweden.

Table S8

Post-hoc Tukey pairwise comparisons of emotional responses between countries: Results from the Survey Study

Stimuli	Emotion	I	J	Mean Diff. (SE)	Stimuli	Emotion	I	J	Mean Diff. (SE)
Income Inequality	Sadness	GB	FR	0.03 (0.04)	Wealth Inequality	Sadness	GB	FR	0.03 (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.23* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.28* (0.04)
		FR	SE	0.21* (0.04)			FR	SE	0.25* (0.04)
	Moral Outrage	GB	FR	-0.25* (0.05)		Moral Outrage	GB	FR	-0.17* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.1 (0.05)			GB	SE	0.28* (0.05)
		FR	SE	0.35* (0.05)			FR	SE	0.45* (0.05)
	Indifference	GB	FR	0.47* (0.04)		Indifference	GB	FR	0.37* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.18* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.15* (0.05)
		FR	SE	-0.29* (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.22* (0.05)
	Contentment	GB	FR	0.31* (0.04)		Contentment	GB	FR	0.27* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.28* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.29* (0.04)
		FR	SE	-0.03 (0.04)			FR	SE	0.01 (0.04)
	Anger	GB	FR	-0.24* (0.05)		Anger	GB	FR	-0.14* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.28* (0.05)			GB	SE	0.37* (0.05)
		FR	SE	0.51* (0.05)			FR	SE	0.51* (0.05)
	Frustration	GB	FR	0.29* (0.05)		Frustration	GB	FR	0.43* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.25* (0.05)			GB	SE	0.39* (0.05)
		FR	SE	-0.04 (0.05)			FR	SE	-0.04 (0.05)
	Compassion	GB	FR	0.30* (0.04)		Compassion	GB	FR	0.31* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.00 (0.04)			GB	SE	0.03 (0.05)
		FR	SE	-0.30* (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.29* (0.05)
	Admiration	GB	FR	0.34* (0.04)		Admiration	GB	FR	0.20* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.25* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.03 (0.04)
		FR	SE	-0.09 (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.18* (0.04)
Poor People	Sadness	GB	FR	-0.16* (0.04)	Social Beneficiaries	Sadness	GB	FR	0.30* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.02 (0.04)			GB	SE	-0.09 (0.05)
		FR	SE	0.17* (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.39* (0.05)
	Moral Outrage	GB	FR	-0.27* (0.05)		Moral Outrage	GB	FR	-0.14* (0.05)
		GB	SE	-0.04 (0.05)			GB	SE	0.16* (0.05)
		FR	SE	0.23* (0.05)			FR	SE	0.31* (0.05)
	Indifference	GB	FR	0.47* (0.04)		Indifference	GB	FR	0.21* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.22* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.20* (0.04)
		FR	SE	-0.26* (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.02 (0.04)
	Contentment	GB	FR	0.34* (0.04)		Contentment	GB	FR	0.23* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.33* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.46* (0.04)
		FR	SE	0.00 (0.04)			FR	SE	0.22* (0.04)
	Anger	GB	FR	-0.23* (0.05)		Anger	GB	FR	-0.22* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.11 (0.05)			GB	SE	0.36* (0.05)
		FR	SE	0.34* (0.05)			FR	SE	0.58* (0.05)
	Frustration	GB	FR	0.42* (0.05)		Frustration	GB	FR	0.52* (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.11 (0.05)			GB	SE	0.24* (0.05)
		FR	SE	-0.32* (0.05)			FR	SE	-0.27* (0.05)
	Compassion	GB	FR	-0.02 (0.04)		Compassion	GB	FR	0.52* (0.05)
		GB	SE	-0.12* (0.04)			GB	SE	-0.17* (0.05)
		FR	SE	-0.11* (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.69* (0.05)
	Admiration	GB	FR	0.48* (0.04)		Admiration	GB	FR	0.38* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.48* (0.04)			GB	SE	0.35* (0.04)
		FR	SE	0.00 (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.04 (0.04)
Rich People	Sadness	GB	FR	0.24* (0.04)	Taxpayers	Sadness	GB	FR	0.10 (0.05)
		GB	SE	-0.09 (0.04)			GB	SE	0.36* (0.05)
		FR	SE	-0.33* (0.04)			FR	SE	0.26* (0.05)
	Moral Outrage	GB	FR	0.06 (0.05)		Moral Outrage	GB	FR	0.04 (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.18* (0.05)			GB	SE	0.24* (0.05)
		FR	SE	0.12 (0.05)			FR	SE	0.21* (0.05)
	Indifference	GB	FR	-0.07 (0.05)		Indifference	GB	FR	0.26* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.23* (0.05)			GB	SE	0.31* (0.04)
		FR	SE	0.30* (0.05)			FR	SE	0.05 (0.04)
	Contentment	GB	FR	0.26* (0.04)		Contentment	GB	FR	0.15* (0.04)
		GB	SE	0.25* (0.04)			GB	SE	-0.02 (0.04)
		FR	SE	-0.01 (0.04)			FR	SE	-0.17* (0.04)
	Anger	GB	FR	0.14* (0.05)		Anger	GB	FR	-0.04 (0.05)
		GB	SE	0.27* (0.05)			GB	SE	0.40* (0.05)

Frustration	FR	SE	0.13* (0.05)
	GB	FR	0.47* (0.05)
	GB	SE	0.21* (0.05)
Compassion	FR	SE	-0.25* (0.05)
	GB	FR	0.32* (0.04)
	GB	SE	-0.01 (0.04)
Admiration	FR	SE	-0.32* (0.04)
	GB	FR	0.11* (0.05)
	GB	SE	0.13* (0.05)
	FR	SE	0.01 (0.05)

Frustration	FR	SE	0.44* (0.05)
	GB	FR	0.24* (0.05)
	GB	SE	0.42* (0.05)
Compassion	FR	SE	0.18* (0.05)
	GB	FR	0.14* (0.05)
	GB	SE	0.07 (0.05)
Admiration	FR	SE	-0.06 (0.05)
	GB	FR	0.34* (0.05)
	GB	SE	0.20* (0.05)
	FR	SE	-0.14* (0.05)

Table S9

Multiple Linear Regression Analyses with Standardized Coefficients from 'Control-Only' Models (without Causal Attributions) Predicting Emotional Responses to Income Inequality: Results from the Survey Study

Country	Control Variables	Sadness	Moral Outrage	Indifference	Contentment	Anger	Frustration	Compassion	Admiration
Britain	Intercept	-0.05	-0.03	0.03	0.10**	-0.04	-0.01	-0.03	0.04
	Age	-0.12***	-0.08**	-0.15***	-0.20***	-0.11***	-0.15***	0.03	-0.19***
	Household income	-0.00	-0.02	-0.04	-0.07*	-0.05	-0.06	-0.01	-0.03
	Education in years	-0.01	0.01	-0.12***	-0.10***	-0.01	0.00	-0.04	-0.13***
	Subj. Social Status	-0.06*	-0.11***	0.13***	0.21***	-0.10**	-0.12***	0.05	0.22***
	Left-Right	-0.21***	-0.20***	0.22***	0.23***	-0.26***	-0.19***	-0.19***	0.18***
	Female	0.16**	0.16**	-0.15*	-0.18**	0.15*	0.10	0.13*	-0.06
	Adj. R ²	0.09	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.13	0.10	0.03	0.15
	N	1,162	1,164	1,156	1,149	1,166	1,165	1,162	1,138
France	Intercept	-0.10*	-0.04	0.07	0.12**	-0.05	-0.05	-0.09*	0.07
	Age	-0.02	0.01	-0.10***	-0.17***	-0.08**	-0.23***	0.03	-0.07*
	Household income	-0.05	-0.02	0.01	-0.03	-0.06	-0.08*	-0.03	-0.05
	Education in years	-0.06	-0.02	0.00	-0.01	-0.06	-0.05	-0.01	-0.02
	Subj. Social Status	-0.08**	-0.14***	0.13***	0.13***	-0.16***	-0.14***	0.13***	0.15***
	Left-Right	-0.19***	-0.20***	0.22***	0.16***	-0.12***	-0.08**	-0.25***	0.13***
	Female	0.19**	0.10	-0.16**	-0.21***	0.09	0.09	0.16**	-0.16**
	Adj. R ²	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.07	0.05
	N	1,121	1,120	1,127	1,101	1,125	1,123	1,113	1,091
Sweden	Intercept	-0.18***	-0.13***	0.12***	0.13***	-0.11**	-0.14***	-0.11**	0.16***
	Age	-0.08**	-0.03	-0.17***	-0.10***	-0.04	-0.07*	-0.10***	-0.15***
	Household income	-0.00	-0.06*	-0.03	-0.05	-0.04	-0.07*	-0.00	-0.01
	Education in years	0.03	0.04	-0.06*	-0.10***	0.03	0.05	0.06*	-0.10***
	Subj. Social Status	-0.11***	-0.08**	0.01	0.19***	-0.12***	-0.12***	0.12***	0.18***
	Left-Right	-0.26***	-0.33***	0.18***	0.13***	-0.26***	-0.26***	-0.23***	0.10***
	Female	0.35***	0.26***	-0.31***	-0.28***	0.22***	0.27***	0.20***	-0.33***
	Adj. R ²	0.15	0.17	0.08	0.09	0.13	0.15	0.08	0.10
	N	1,218	1,203	1,194	1,186	1,216	1,214	1,213	1,176

Note. Model without Income Inequality Attributions and only with Control variables included. $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***). All independent and dependent variables were standardized (z-scores) using R's scale function prior to conducting the regression. The reported coefficients are therefore equivalent to standardized beta coefficients (β), allowing direct comparison of effect sizes across predictors.

Table S10

Multiple Linear Regression Analyses with Standardized Coefficients from 'Control-Only' Models (without Causal Attributions) Predicting Emotional Responses to Wealth Inequality: Results from the Survey Study

Country	Control Variables	Moral							
		Sadness	Outrage	Indifference	Contentment	Anger	Frustration	Compassion	Admiration
Britain	Intercept	-0.03	-0.05	0.06	0.09*	-0.03	-0.08*	-0.04	0.05
	Age	-0.14***	-0.09**	-0.11***	-0.16***	-0.10***	-0.12***	0.06	-0.12***
	Household income	-0.01	-0.01	-0.08*	-0.04	-0.02	0.01	0.00	-0.10**
	Education in years	0.01	-0.03	-0.10***	-0.09**	0.01	0.02	-0.02	-0.13***
	Subj. Social Status	-0.10**	-0.04	0.08*	0.18***	-0.13***	-0.16***	0.13***	0.23***
	Left-Right	-0.16***	-0.25***	0.26***	0.27***	-0.26***	-0.22***	-0.11***	0.22***
	Female	0.10	0.11	-0.14*	-0.16**	0.08	0.18**	0.19**	-0.06
	Adj. R ²	0.07	0.09	0.12	0.17	0.13	0.13	0.02	0.15
N	1,147	1,144	1,139	1,120	1,151	1,152	1,144	1,119	
France	Intercept	-0.08	-0.07	0.17***	0.15***	-0.10*	-0.05	-0.08	0.08*
	Age	-0.00	0.06	-0.10***	-0.16***	-0.03	-0.17***	-0.05	-0.08**
	Household income	-0.11***	-0.09**	0.02	-0.08**	-0.16***	-0.12***	-0.03	-0.05
	Education in years	-0.04	-0.06	-0.07*	-0.01	-0.03	-0.06*	0.01	-0.09**
	Subj. Social Status	-0.00	-0.06*	0.09**	0.18***	-0.07*	-0.07*	0.15***	0.17***
	Left-Right	-0.21***	-0.28***	0.23***	0.15***	-0.22***	-0.12***	-0.20***	0.14***
	Female	0.18**	0.11	-0.29***	-0.27***	0.15**	0.08	0.14*	-0.14*
	Adj. R ²	0.07	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.09	0.06	0.06
N	1,148	1,144	1,141	1,119	1,149	1,140	1,134	1,115	
Sweden	Intercept	-0.13***	-0.03	0.04	0.11**	-0.09*	-0.09*	-0.12**	0.12**
	Age	-0.13***	-0.07**	-0.09**	-0.10***	-0.08**	-0.12***	-0.14***	-0.11***
	Household income	-0.07**	-0.04	0.01	-0.01	-0.06*	-0.06*	-0.00	-0.01
	Education in years	-0.05*	-0.00	-0.05	-0.09**	-0.04	0.02	-0.05	-0.03
	Subj. Social Status	-0.09**	-0.08*	0.05	0.16***	-0.12***	-0.16***	0.05	0.16***
	Left-Right	-0.28***	-0.36***	0.24***	0.18***	-0.28***	-0.31***	-0.21***	0.22***
	Female	0.25***	0.12*	-0.09	-0.22***	0.20***	0.19***	0.26***	-0.25***
	Adj. R ²	0.17	0.17	0.08	0.09	0.16	0.20	0.09	0.11
N	1,195	1,190	1,172	1,176	1,204	1,212	1,184	1,169	

Note. Model without Wealth Inequality Attributions and only with Control variables included. $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***). All independent and dependent variables were standardized (z-scores) using R's scale function prior to conducting the regression. The reported coefficients are therefore equivalent to standardized beta coefficients (β), allowing direct comparison of effect sizes across predictors.

Table S11

Multiple linear regression analyses of emotional responses to income inequality regressed on causal attributions including Trade Unions and Can't choose response options: Results from the Survey Study

		Sadness	Moral Outrage	Indifference	Contentment	Anger	Frustration	Compassion	Admiration	
Income Inequality	Britain	Private companies	-0.17*	-0.17*	0.02	-0.10	-0.26**	-0.22**	-0.12	0.02
		High-income individuals	-0.11	-0.10	0.21*	0.12	-0.07	-0.08	0.01	0.12
		Low-income individuals	-0.88***	-0.96***	0.34**	0.24*	-0.85***	-0.89***	-0.61***	0.11
		Trade unions	-0.43**	-0.65***	0.35*	0.46**	-0.74***	-0.60***	-0.07	0.33*
		Can't choose	-0.49***	-0.73***	0.24*	0.02	-0.65***	-0.75***	-0.19	0.05
		(Intercept)	0.16**	0.21***	-0.07	0.06	0.20***	0.24***	0.09	0.00
		Adj. R ²	0.15	0.18	0.14	0.18	0.20	0.19	0.06	0.15
		N	1,421	1,417	1,398	1,385	1,426	1,428	1,414	1,377
	France	Private companies	-0.14	-0.11	0.13	0.06	-0.28***	-0.21**	0.04	0.10
		High-income individuals	-0.01	-0.16	0.20*	0.21*	-0.26**	-0.16	-0.04	0.18
		Low-income individuals	-0.54***	-0.90***	0.74***	0.48***	-0.95***	-0.79***	-0.04	0.35**
		Trade unions	-0.23	-0.42**	0.17	0.44**	-0.47**	-0.27	0.10	0.41*
		Can't choose	-0.36***	-0.32**	0.06	0.11	-0.63***	-0.40***	0.09	0.08
		(Intercept)	0.02	0.13*	-0.06	0.01	0.21***	0.13*	-0.11	-0.02
		Adj. R ²	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.14	0.15	0.07	0.06
		N	1,465	1,453	1,467	1,431	1,465	1,466	1,446	1,424
	Sweden	Private companies	-0.17*	-0.20**	0.04	0.10	-0.05	-0.18*	-0.07	0.10
		High-income individuals	-0.03	-0.11	0.09	0.07	-0.15	-0.12	0.02	0.11
		Low-income individuals	-0.76***	-0.93***	0.21*	0.12	-0.83***	-0.88***	-0.57***	0.07
		Trade unions	-0.34*	-0.43**	0.36*	0.20	-0.27	-0.14	-0.18	0.61***
		Can't choose	-0.33**	-0.50***	0.07	0.03	-0.53***	-0.50***	-0.08	-0.02
(Intercept)		-0.01	0.11*	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.00	0.10	
Adj. R ²		0.19	0.24	0.09	0.09	0.18	0.21	0.10	0.11	
N		1,429	1,416	1,399	1,390	1,434	1,440	1,422	1,384	

Note. Control variables included are: Age, Gender, Income, Education, Social subjective status, and political orientation Left–Right. $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***). The reference category for causal attributions is Government. Regression coefficients (b) are reported.

Table S12

Multiple linear regression analyses of emotional responses to wealth inequality regressed on causal attributions including Trade Unions and Can't choose response options: Results from the Survey Study

		Sadness	Moral Outrage	Indifference	Contentment	Anger	Frustration	Compassion	Admiration	
Wealth Inequality	Britain	Private companies	-0.30***	-0.30***	0.02	0.12	-0.38***	-0.20*	-0.17*	0.19*
		High-income individuals	-0.08	-0.12	0.00	-0.03	-0.12	-0.12	-0.11	0.44*
		Low-income individuals	-0.64***	-0.92***	0.38***	0.43***	-0.76***	-0.76***	-0.01	-0.01
		Trade unions	-0.45**	-0.30	0.20	0.28	-0.55**	-0.38*	-0.59***	0.33**
		Can't choose	-0.25*	-0.57***	0.05	-0.01	-0.52***	-0.42***	-0.07	-0.05
		(Intercept)	0.14**	0.17**	0.01	0.04	0.18***	0.09	0.06	0.00
		Adj. R ²	0.09	0.15	0.13	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.05	0.17
		N	1,436	1,427	1,426	1,397	1,450	1,448	1,433	1,395
	France	Private companies	-0.06	-0.10	0.09	0.15	-0.20*	-0.29**	0.14	0.12
		High-income individuals	-0.02	-0.08	0.10	0.00	-0.10	-0.18*	0.11	0.06
		Low-income individuals	-0.53***	-0.73***	0.64***	0.35**	-0.68***	-0.67***	0.03	0.41**
		Trade unions	-0.53**	-0.39*	0.39*	0.09	-0.55**	-0.24	-0.07	0.45*
		Can't choose	-0.31**	-0.63***	0.27**	0.13	-0.63***	-0.53***	0.06	0.08
		(Intercept)	0.04	0.12*	0.02	0.11	0.11*	0.17**	-0.13*	-0.01
		Adj. R ²	0.09	0.16	0.12	0.10	0.16	0.13	0.06	0.08
		N	1,452	1,448	1,450	1,413	1,461	1,454	1,433	1,408
	Sweden	Private companies	-0.14	-0.14	-0.03	0.07	-0.21*	-0.27**	-0.09	0.06
		High-income individuals	-0.15*	-0.20**	0.09	0.10	-0.21**	-0.24**	-0.11	0.18*
Low-income individuals		-0.59***	-0.63***	0.34**	0.42***	-0.59***	-0.56***	-0.36**	0.39***	
Trade unions		0.09	0.06	0.34	0.49**	-0.03	-0.10	0.00	0.50**	
Can't choose		-0.46***	-0.60***	0.04	-0.03	-0.59***	-0.58***	-0.29**	-0.12	
(Intercept)		0.04	0.17***	-0.02	0.00	0.12*	0.13**	-0.01	0.00	
Adj. R ²		0.20	0.21	0.09	0.11	0.19	0.23	0.10	0.12	
N		1,420	1,416	1,388	1,392	1,435	1,447	1,412	1,389	

Note. Control variables included are: Age, Gender, Income, Education, Social subjective status, and political orientation Left–Right. $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***). The reference category for causal attributions is Government. Regression coefficients (b) are reported.

Table S13*Change in adjusted R² with inclusion of (income and wealth) inequality attributions*

Country	Dependent variable	N base	N full	Adj. R² base	Adj. R² full	Adj. R² diff
<i>Income Inequality</i>						
Britain	Sadness	1,019	983	0.07	0.14	0.07
	Moral Outrage	1,021	985	0.08	0.16	0.08
	Indifference	1,012	976	0.13	0.14	0.01
	Contentment	1,007	972	0.18	0.18	0.00
	Anger	1,021	985	0.12	0.18	0.06
	Frustration	1,022	987	0.10	0.17	0.07
	Compassion	1,017	981	0.03	0.06	0.03
	Admiration	997	962	0.16	0.16	0.00
France	Sadness	953	900	0.06	0.08	0.02
	Moral Outrage	953	900	0.07	0.12	0.05
	Indifference	960	906	0.09	0.12	0.03
	Contentment	946	893	0.09	0.10	0.01
	Anger	955	903	0.07	0.14	0.06
	Frustration	954	902	0.10	0.14	0.04
	Compassion	950	896	0.07	0.07	0.00
	Admiration	936	885	0.06	0.07	0.01
Sweden	Sadness	1,068	1,019	0.14	0.19	0.05
	Moral Outrage	1,058	1,007	0.17	0.24	0.07
	Indifference	1,050	999	0.09	0.09	0.00
	Contentment	1,041	994	0.10	0.11	0.01
	Anger	1,067	1,018	0.14	0.19	0.05
	Frustration	1,069	1,019	0.15	0.22	0.07
	Compassion	1,063	1,014	0.08	0.11	0.03
	Admiration	1,041	995	0.10	0.11	0.01
<i>Wealth Inequality</i>						
Britain	Sadness	1,011	978	0.06	0.09	0.03
	Moral Outrage	1,007	974	0.08	0.15	0.07
	Indifference	1,005	972	0.12	0.14	0.02
	Contentment	989	957	0.18	0.20	0.02
	Anger	1,014	981	0.12	0.17	0.05
	Frustration	1,015	982	0.12	0.17	0.05
	Compassion	1,010	977	0.02	0.04	0.02
	Admiration	992	961	0.15	0.17	0.02
France	Sadness	986	933	0.07	0.08	0.01
	Moral Outrage	982	928	0.13	0.16	0.03
	Indifference	982	928	0.11	0.13	0.02
	Contentment	963	910	0.11	0.12	0.01
	Anger	988	935	0.12	0.14	0.02
	Frustration	981	928	0.09	0.12	0.03
	Compassion	977	925	0.06	0.06	0.00
	Admiration	960	907	0.08	0.09	0.01
Sweden	Sadness	1,021	992	0.19	0.21	0.02
	Moral Outrage	1,018	989	0.18	0.20	0.02
	Indifference	1,006	977	0.09	0.10	0.01
	Contentment	1,007	977	0.10	0.11	0.01
	Anger	1,029	999	0.17	0.18	0.01
	Frustration	1,033	1,003	0.21	0.22	0.01
	Compassion	1,006	976	0.09	0.09	0.00
	Admiration	1,002	973	0.12	0.12	0.00

Note. N base refers to the number of observations used in the “base” model, including only control variables. N full refers to the number of observations used in the “full” model, including both control variables and causal attributions.